

**THERMAL SPIKE EFFECTS ON MOISTURE ABSORPTION
BY A BISMALLEIMIDE MODIFIED EPOXY/CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITE**

Z D Xiang and F R Jones
Department of Engineering Materials
University of Sheffield
Sheffield, S1 4DU, England

ABSTRACT

Moisture diffusion and absorption behaviour in a bismaleimide modified epoxy/carbon fibre composite were studied under both constant hygrothermal and thermal spike conditions. Thermal spikes to temperatures in excess of 100°C cause an enhanced moisture absorption. Since there is no physical damage to the composite, the observations can be explained by changes in free volume of the matrix at spiking temperatures. These changes are found by comparison of the desorption and reabsorption curves, to be irreversible. A retention of mass after drying suggests that some hydrolysis may have occurred which affects the free volume and polarity of the matrix.

Keywords: Carbon fibre composites, BMI/Epoxy matrix, Moisture absorption, Thermal spiking

1. INTRODUCTION

Of major concern for the structural application of epoxy/carbon fibre composites is their tendency to absorb moisture in humid environments (1). Moisture absorption deteriorates the thermomechanical performance of a composite through the plasticisation of the polymer matrix which results in a decrease in the glass transition temperature and hence the maximum service temperature. Cured epoxy resins are particularly sensitive to moisture (2,3). A further undesirable effect is the dimensional instability arising from moisture induced swelling. The magnitude of these effects depend on the quantity of moisture absorbed. At equilibrium at low temperatures up to 100°C, it depends only on the relative humidity of the environment. However, under more severe hygrothermal conditions such as thermal spikes at temperatures higher than 100°C, recent studies have shown that the composites can absorb significantly larger quantities of moisture than under equivalent isothermal hygrothermal conditions (3-5). This study was therefore carried out to identify the thermal spiking conditions at which the enhanced moisture absorption occurred. In this way the mechanisms responsible could be delineated. In a previous study (6) it was shown that thermal spiking to temperatures near to the glass transition of the matrix led to matrix cracking in crossply laminates. A critical temperature for the wet laminates was identified from a consideration of the enhancement in residual thermal strain which occurred on cooling the wet laminate, which had a larger transverse expansion coefficient, from a thermal spike. In this paper we examine in more detail the effects occurring at lower maximum temperatures.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

This study focussed on crossply laminates O₂/90/O₂ manufactured from Narmco Rigidite 5245C prepreg. The prepreg tape was cut to the required size and layed-up into the required laminate configuration and cured in a press-clave at 177°C for 2 hours. The bagging and curing procedures were in accordance with the manufacturer's specifications. The glass transition temperatures of the matrix in the wet and dry postcured laminates were determined on a Polymer Laboratories DMTA at 1Hz.

2.2 Coupon Preparation and Conditioning

The cured laminates were cut into plates with dimensions of 60x50mm using a water cooled diamond cutting wheel. The edges of the sample were then ground and polished to a 1200 grit finish followed by post-curing at 210°C for 4 hours using the recommended schedule. After post-curing the samples were further dried in a vacuum oven at 50°C under full vacuum until a constant weight was attained. It was found that drying for one week under such conditions was sufficient for this laminate which was 0.648 mm thick.

The coupons were divided into two groups: control and spiking specimens: the controls were conditioned under a constant hygrothermal environment without subjecting them to a thermal spike. Spiking specimens were conditioned under the same environment but subjected to intermittent thermal spikes. Both groups were conditioned in a humidity chamber under 96%RH at 45°C. The relative humidity was established in a glass chamber using a saturated solution of K₂SO₄. The moisture content of individual specimens was determined by removing them from the humidity chamber at various intervals and weighing them on a Mettler AE 240 electrobalance at an accuracy of 10⁻⁵g. Moisture content, M_t, was expressed conventionally as the percentage increase in sample weight:

$$M_t = 100(m_t - m_0)/m_0 \quad (1)$$

where m₀ and m_t are the dry sample weight and wet sample weight at time t respectively.

2.3 Thermal Spiking Programmes

Thermal spiking was carried out in an air circulating oven at a series of temperatures according to the spiking programmes set out in Table 1. Thermal spikes were applied by rapid transfer of the coupons to the spiking oven, preheated to the required temperature for

Table 1. Thermal spiking programmes

Spiking Temperature (°C)	Spiking Time (mins)
100	3.0
120	3.5
140	4.0
160	4.5

the specified period. They were then removed and cooled to room temperature. The spiking times were chosen to ensure that the temperature became uniform within the specimens and held at that level for approximately 1 minute. During spiking the specimens were held vertically in a steel frame to ensure uniform heating. The first thermal spike was applied after the coupons had been conditioned in the humidity chamber for ≈ 1 day. The specimens were then returned to the humidity chamber until applying the next thermal spike. The moisture content was recorded before and after a thermal spike. This routine was subsequently repeated at regular intervals.

The moisture diffusion coefficient (D_c) was calculated by assuming that moisture diffusion into the composite followed the Fick equation for one dimensional diffusion with a constant diffusion coefficient, D_c . It can be shown that the diffusion coefficient can be determined using the following equation:

$$D = \pi(sd/4M_\infty)^2 \quad (2)$$

where s is the initial slope of the plot of M_t against \sqrt{t} , d is sample thickness and M_∞ is the moisture content at equilibrium. Since D is obtained from coupons with finite dimensions it needs to be corrected for diffusion through the edges (7). Therefore

$$D_c = D(1 + d/l + d/h)^{-2} \quad (3)$$

where l and h are sample length and width respectively.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Characteristics of Moisture Absorption Under Thermal Spiking

Fig 1 compares the typical moisture absorption curve for specimens which have been subjected to intermittent thermal spikes to 140°C with that for control specimens subjected only to an isothermal temperature of 45°C at 96%RH. Each datum point is an average of measurements on four specimens. The saw-tooth shape of the absorption curve for spiking specimens results from partial drying at the spiking temperature. The absorption curve for the control specimens indicated that the diffusion process was not completely Fickian because the moisture concentration continued to rise, although very slowly, during prolonged conditioning. Taking the last reading of 0.80 wt% as M_∞ , D_c is computed to be $4.47 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mm}^2/\text{s}$, which is in agreement with results from other epoxy resin matrix carbon fibre composites. The spiked coupons clearly exhibited higher moisture absorption even after the second thermal spike. Subsequent thermal spikes caused a sharp rise in moisture absorption in a manner almost proportional to the number of thermal spikes.

3.2 Effect of Spiking Temperature

Fig 2 shows the effect of spiking temperature on moisture absorption. The weight after intermittent drying during spiking is omitted for the purpose of clarity. Thermal spiking had a small but measurable enhancing effect at a spiking temperature of 100°C. The strongest enhancement occurred in the temperature region of 120°C to 140°C. Further increases in spiking temperature beyond 140°C did not result in further enhancement. Instead, after prolonged conditioning and spiking the moisture content of the 160°C spiked specimens increased at a lower rate and eventually became less than that in the 140°C spiked specimens. This is more clearly illustrated in Fig 3

Figure 1 Moisture absorption of 0₂/90/0₂ laminate subjected to a thermal spike.

Figure 2 The effect of the thermal spiking temperature on moisture absorption of a 0₂/90/0₂ laminate. The intermittent reduction in weight (see Fig 1) is omitted.

Figure 3 Thermal spiking temperature dependence of moisture absorption after differing time intervals \sqrt{t}/d (a) 40.3 (■) and (b) 77.5 \sqrt{h}/mm (●).

which shows a plot of moisture content at the intervals of $\sqrt{t}/d = 40.3$ and $77.5 \sqrt{h}/mm$ as a function of spiking temperature.

3.3 Desorption and Reabsorption Curves

The enhanced moisture absorption behaviour under thermal spike conditions may indicate the occurrence of certain changes in the structure of the polymer matrix, or indeed physical damage to the composite. In order to establish if these effects were irreversible, all the specimens were dried in a vacuum oven at 45°C, and then isothermally reconditioned at 96 RH% and 45°C in the absence of a thermal spike. Fig 4 and Fig 5 show the desorption and reabsorption curves respectively. The desorption curves revealed the presence of a residual weight increase which might arise in a small concentration of unremovable "residual moisture", which increased with thermal spiking temperature. On reabsorption, however, the moisture content in the specimens all returned to the levels established at corresponding thermal spiking temperatures. This confirmed that the changes induced during thermal spiking were irreversible. Microscopic observation, however, showed no evidence of any physical damage in the form of microcracks.

Since there is no anomalous behaviour during isothermal desorption and reabsorption, the moisture diffusion coefficients for the thermally spiked coupons can be estimated and compared with those for original absorption by the control specimens. From the data given in Table 2, a decrease in D_c with spiking temperature is evident, especially for those coupons which have experienced temperatures at and above 140°C.

Table 2. Moisture diffusion coefficients from absorption, desorption and reabsorption processes

Spiking Temperature/°C	$D_c/10^{-7}mm^2/s$		
	Absorption	Desorption	Reabsorption
Control	4.47	4.46	3.96
100°C	-	4.36	4.04
120°C	-	4.35	3.67
140°C	-	3.72	2.08
160°C	-	2.66	2.29

4. DISCUSSION

It has been shown that thermal spiking to 100°C had a small but measurable enhancing effect on the moisture absorption by these crossply laminates at 45°C and 96%RH. However, at temperatures of 120°C to 140°C the enhancement was significantly greater. The DMTA trace for a laminate saturated with moisture isothermally at 96% RH and 45°C is given in Fig 6. This shows the glass transition region extends from 100°C to 250°C with the major relaxation event occurring above 160°C. The coincidence of the thermal spiking temperature for maximum enhancement with the onset of the glass transition of the wet resin must be significant. Since no physical damage in the form of microcracks could be found, the increase in moisture absorption appears to be related to an increase in free volume in polymer matrix at the elevated temperatures. For example, Aronhime, Peng and Gillham (8) have shown that an increased free volume as a result of higher degrees of cure can lead to higher moisture absorption in high humidity environments. They also postulated that increased

Figure 4 Moisture desorption curves at 50°C for laminates previously thermally spiked to differing temperatures.

Figure 5 Moisture reabsorption curves at 96%RH, 45°C for laminates which had been thermally spiked and subsequently desorbed.

crosslink density arising from higher degrees of cure leads to a decrease in moisture diffusion coefficient.

Other studies have shown that identical thermal spikes on dry composites did not lead to a higher moisture absorption in subsequent conditioning in a constant hygrothermal environment (4). Thus the mechanisms responsible for the moisture enhancement on thermal spiking only operate in a wet laminate during intermittent excursions to higher temperatures. At spiking temperatures, apart from the drying process, additional free volume is created into which the moisture can diffuse and which would otherwise not be available for the accommodation of moisture at normal conditioning temperatures between 20 to 60°C. During rapid cooling, the moisture in this additional free volume is fixed, leaving a larger population of normal sites into which moisture can enter during subsequent conditioning. It is therefore not surprising to find that the moisture absorption increases in a manner proportional to the number of thermal spikes applied. The free volume in the matrix increases with temperature, leading to higher moisture absorption at higher spiking temperatures. However, as shown in Fig 2, after prolonged spiking and conditioning treatments, the 160°C spiked specimens showed less stronger enhancement than those spiked at 140°C. Such an inversion did not occur for the coupons conditioned in an environment of a lower relative humidity but spiked under the same conditions (9). Therefore, it may be due to a high humidity high spiking temperature induced degradation which may result in molecular relaxation of the polymer network, but not necessarily a reduction in weight of the laminates. The desorption curves exhibited a residual weight which was highest for the specimens spiked at 160°C, inferring that some water was chemically reacted in the composite presumably with the matrix. Therefore the apparent residual moisture content could be in the form of either hydrolysis products or strongly hydrogen bonded water molecules. Close examination of Fig 6 suggests that the mobility of the polymer molecules would favour the kinetics of hydrolysis above 160°C.

Figure 6 The dynamic thermomechanical response (DMTA) of an isothermally moisture conditioned laminate.

The diffusion coefficient determined from the desorption and reabsorption curves decreased with the spiking temperature which the laminates had previously experienced. This also appears to confirm the microscopy results that thermal spiking to temperatures up to 160°C did not result in significant physical damage since with microcracking D_c was expected to increase rather than decrease.

The reduction in diffusion constant for reabsorption of moisture along with the apparent permanent retention of "absorbed water" after desorption might suggest that hydrolysis was accompanied by an increase in crosslink density. However, it is unlikely that hydrolysis would lead to crosslinking through a covalent bond formation, but molecular relaxation could enable secondary intermolecular interactions to occur with the same result.

CONCLUSIONS

The enhanced moisture absorption of Narmco 5245C based laminates as a result of thermal spiking during hygrothermal conditioning has been confirmed. The lowest spike temperature at which this phenomenon is observed is the onset of the glass transition in the wet resin which occurs at 100°C. Maximum enhancement occurs at 140°C which suggests that changes and/or distribution in free volume plays a significant role in the mechanism.

REFERENCES

1. Morgan, R.J. and O'Neal, J.E., *Polymer Plast Tech and Eng*, **10**, (1978), 49.
2. Bueche, F. and Kelley, F.N., *J Polymer Sci*, **45** (1960), 267-273.
3. Collings, T.A. and Stone, D.E.W., *Composite Structure*, **3**, (1985), 341-378.
4. Clark, G., Saunders, D.S., van Blaricum, T.J. and Richmond, M., *Comp Sci Tech*, **39**, (1990), 355-375.
5. Browning, C., *Polymer Engineering Science*, **18**, (1978), pp 16-24.
6. Jacobs, P.M. and Jones, F.R., *The mechanism of enhanced moisture absorption and damage accumulation in composites exposed to thermal spikes*, in *Composites, Design, Manufacture and Application* (Ed S.W. Tsai and G.S. Springer), Sampe, Corning, USA, Vol 2, Chapter 15, paper D.
7. Shen, C.H. and Springer, G.S., *J Comp Materials*, **10**, (1976), 2-10.
8. Aronhime, M.T., Peng, X. and Gillham, J.K., *J Appl Polymer Sci*, **32**, (1986), 3589-3626.
9. Xiang, Z.D. and Jones, F.R., Unpublished results.